

Love, Life, and Literacy: How Civil Status Shapes Teachers' Financial Savvy

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Abstract. The purpose of this study was to determine the significant difference on the financial savvy when grouped according to civil status. This study used the descriptive-comparative research design. The respondents of this study were the teachers of Dr. P. Ocampo Colleges, Inc., District 8; Division of Cotabato City. The researcher used the universal sampling method in selecting the respondents. The gathered data were analyzed and interpreted by using the statistical tools frequency and percentage, mean, and One-way ANOVA. The results revealed that on the civil status profile of teachers, most teachers are married, with fewer being single, widowed, or legally separated. Moreover, on the level of teachers' financial savvy in terms of money management, credit and debt management, and Planning, Saving, and Investing was revealed as high. Meanwhile, in terms of risk management, the results revealed a moderate result. Further, it was found that there is a statistically significant difference between financial savvy when grouped according to civil status. Lastly, based on the findings, it is evident that among the respondents, teachers who are legally separated and widowed may have a greater need for financial literacy training. Thus, this study recommends, the Department of Education to integrate financial literacy into the professional development programs, the department can foster a more financially savvy teaching workforce.

KEY WORDS

1. Civil status
2. financial savvy
3. teachers
4. money management
5. Descriptive-comparative

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1. Introduction

Globally, financial literacy is recognized as essential for both the survival and expansion of the economy and financial system. As a result, there is a growing need for fundamental financial knowledge in a world that is becoming increasingly complex. The necessity of financial education interventions is underscored by the prevalence of low financial literacy or capability levels in both developed and developing countries. In the Philippines, the challenge of enhancing financial literacy persists. It is imper-

ative that a greater number of Filipinos acquire a deeper understanding of fundamental financial principles and become more financially literate. This lack of literacy results in financial hardship for Filipinos, including the necessity of preparing for emergencies and failing to meet their regular spending requirements.

Lopez et al. (2024) conducted a study in Davao City to evaluate the financial literacy of basic education teachers. The study identified several critical themes that influence their finan-

cial literacy, such as emotional distress, financial strain, and the impact of these factors on teaching performance. Teachers reported financial difficulties that were further exacerbated by challenges such as insufficient income and reliance on informal financing.

With so many teachers experiencing challenges with their finances, it is critical to understand how their civil status affects financial literacy. This is because teachers' entire household financial status is intrinsically related to their financial literacy, which influences their capacity to make educated financial choices. Hence, this study seeks to understand the emotional and relational dynamics that influence teachers' financial decision-making processes by investigating the interaction of civil status and financial literacy. This insight is crucial for creating targeted initiatives that can help teachers navigate financial issues. Teachers play a critical role in shaping future generations' financial literacy, therefore enhancing their own financial competencies is critical for creating a more financially literate society as a whole.

The study pursued answers to the ensuing objectives: a.) to determine the civil status profile of the respondents. b.) to determine the level of teacher's financial savvy in terms of money management, credit and debt management, planning, saving, and investing, and risk management. c.) to determine if there a significant difference in teacher's financial savvy when grouped according to civil status, and

The following section outlines the procedures used by the researcher to perform this research study. It includes the population and sampling, instrumentation, data source, and data analysis.

1.1. Research Design —This study used a descriptive-comparative methodology to analyze the financial savvy of teachers based on their civil status, focusing on systematically de-

d.) to determine which among the respondents needs financial literacy training.

At .05 level of significance, the following hypothesis was tested: a.) There is no significant difference in teacher's financial savvy when grouped according to civil status.

The study's findings offered valuable insights to various stakeholders: the Department of Education could use the results to develop targeted financial literacy programs addressing teachers' diverse needs based on civil status, optimizing resource allocation and training; school heads could identify teacher groups needing specific financial support and design tailored wellness initiatives; teachers were encouraged to seek financial education to improve decision-making and well-being; students benefited indirectly as financially savvy teachers could better impart financial skills, fostering early positive habits; and future researchers gained a foundation for exploring how demographic factors like civil status influence financial literacy, informing more effective program designs.

Figure 1 illustrated the conceptual framework that depicted the interaction of the variables in the study. The independent variable was the civil status profile of teachers (single, married, widowed, legally separated). On the other hand, the dependent variable of the study was the teachers' financial savvy in terms of money management, credit and debt management, planning, saving and investing, and risk management.

scribing and comparing groups without manipulating variables or establishing causality. By examining differences and similarities among single, married, widowed, and legally separated teachers, the research identified patterns in financial knowledge and decision-making. This approach provided valuable insights into how civil status influences teachers' financial literacy, offering data that can inform educational

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

policies and professional development aimed at enhancing teachers’ financial skills, ultimately supporting better financial education for students and contributing to broader economic stability.

1.2. Ethical Considerations —The researcher adhered to ethical guidelines ensuring confidentiality, informed consent, and voluntary participation, protecting participants’ rights and privacy. The study’s social value supports tailored financial literacy programs for teachers based on civil status, benefiting educators and students. Minimal risks focused on data privacy, with safeguards to prevent coercion and maintain anonymity. The qualified researcher used adequate resources and followed data security laws. Fairness and justice were ensured by treating all participants equally and compensating their time, while transparency was maintained through clear communication and sharing of results with the educational community.

1.3. Research Respondents —This study involved all 75 teachers from Dr. P. Ocampo Colleges, Inc., District 8, Cotabato City, using universal sampling to include the entire population and avoid sampling bias. This approach

ensured comprehensive, reliable insights into teachers’ financial savvy, examining how civil status (single, married, widowed, or legally separated) influenced their financial literacy. Surveys gathered data to support targeted professional development programs aimed at enhancing financial education for both teachers and students. Inclusion criteria required respondents to be active, regular or permanent Basic Education teachers with at least two years of service, while those not meeting these criteria were excluded to ensure relevant and valid findings aligned with the local educational context.

1.4. Research Instrument —This study used an adapted 20-item survey questionnaire from Tilan Cabal (2021) to assess teachers’ financial savvy across four dimensions: money management, credit and debt management, planning, saving and investing, and risk management. The questionnaire demonstrated strong reliability with a Cronbach’s alpha of .89 and was validated by experts to ensure content relevance and alignment with the study’s goals. A pilot test further confirmed its effectiveness, making the instrument a reliable and valid tool for gathering meaningful data on teachers’ fi-

nancial literacy.

1.5. Data Gathering Procedure —The data collection process began with securing formal permission from the Graduate School Dean and Division Superintendent, followed by notifying school heads to ensure institutional consent. The questionnaire underwent rigorous content validation by expert panelists through face-to-face evaluations, leading to revisions based on their feedback. A pilot test with 30 teachers confirmed the instrument’s reliability under conditions similar to the main study. Surveys were then distributed and administered face-to-face to build rapport and encourage thoughtful responses, with completed questionnaires promptly collected and securely stored to main-

tain data integrity. Finally, data analysis was conducted using SPSS, enabling thorough statistical examination aligned with institutional standards to ensure reliable and valid results.

1.6. Data Analysis —To address the research questions, several statistical tools were used: frequency and percentage to describe the respondents’ demographic profile by civil status; mean to evaluate teachers’ financial savvy across money management, credit and debt management, planning, saving and investing, and risk management; and One-Way ANOVA to determine if significant differences existed in financial savvy among teachers grouped by civil status.

2. Results

This chapter delineated the findings and discussion of the research. The presentation commenced with a comprehensive discourse on the civil status profile of the respondents in terms of single, married, widowed, and legally separated. The chapter thereafter included an investigation of the level of teachers’ financial savvy in terms of money management; credit and debt management; planning, saving, and investing; and risk management. The subsequent section discussed the significant difference in teacher’s financial savvy when grouped according to civil status. The end part determined the respondents that need financial literacy training.

2.1. Civil Status Profile of Teachers —Table 1 displayed the data on the civil status profile of teachers. The findings indicated that the majority of teachers were married, with 30 respondents, accounting for 50 percent of the total responses. This was followed by single teachers,

with 19 respondents or 31.67 percent. Widowed teachers accounted for 7 respondents or 11.67 percent, while legally separated teachers had the lowest frequency, with 4 respondents, representing 6.67 percent. These results suggest that most teachers are married, with fewer being single, widowed, or legally separated.

Table 1. Civil Status Profile of Teachers

No.	Civil Status Profile	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
1	Single	19	50.00
2	Married	30	31.67
3	Widowed	7	11.67
4	Legally Separated	4	6.67
Overall		60	100.00

2.2. Level of Teacher’s Financial Savvy —

Table 2 shows the summary on the level of teachers' financial savvy, which was measured by four indicators, namely: Money Management, Credit and Debt Management, Planning, Saving, and Investing, and Risk Management. The mean ratings of these indicators are as follows: Money Management (3.49), which was described as high; Planning, Saving, and Investing (3.43), also described as high; Credit and Debt Management (3.41), described as high; and Risk Management (3.38), described as moderate. The four indicators on the level of teachers' financial savvy generated an overall mean rating of 3.43, described as high. This indicates that teachers' financial savvy in terms of money management, credit and debt management, planning, saving, and investing, and risk management was oftentimes evident.

Table 2. Level of Teacher's Financial Savvy

No.	Item	Mean	Descriptive Level
1	Money Management	3.49	High
2	Credit and Debt Management	3.41	High
3	Planning, Saving, and Investing	3.43	High
4	Risk Management	3.38	Moderate
Overall Mean		3.43	High

Legend: 1.00–1.79 = Very Low, 1.80–2.59 = Low, 2.60–3.39 = Moderate, 3.40–4.19 = High, 4.20–5.00 = Very High.

2.3. *Significant Difference in Teacher's Financial Savvy When Grouped According To Civil Status*—The findings in Table 3 revealed a significant difference in the level of teachers' financial savvy when grouped according to civil status. The computed F-value of 1.044 and the p-value of .000, which is less than the standard level of significance of 0.05, indicate that there is a statistically significant difference between

the variables. This suggests that the civil status of teachers has a significant impact on their level of financial savvy. Given the p-value of .000, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in teachers' financial savvy when grouped according to civil status was rejected, confirming that civil status plays a crucial role in influencing teachers' financial management skills.

Table 3. Significant Difference in Teacher's Financial Savvy When Grouped According to Civil Status

Variable Paired	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Descriptive Interpretation
Teacher's Financial Savvy and Civil Status Profile	191.645	14	14.156	1.044	.000***	Significant

Note. ***p < .001. A significant difference was found in teacher's financial savvy when grouped according to civil status.

2.3.1. *Respondents Who Need Financial Literacy Training*—Based on the findings, it is evident that among the respondents, teachers who are legally separated and widowed may

have a greater need for financial literacy training. Although the overall financial savvy of the teachers is generally high, the significant difference in financial literacy levels when grouped

according to civil status suggests that certain groups are less financially knowledgeable or confident. Since single and married teachers tend to show higher financial savvy, those in more vulnerable civil status categories could benefit from targeted training to improve their financial management skills.

The data indicates that while teachers generally possess strong skills in money management, credit and debt management, and planning, saving, and investing, their proficiency in risk management is only moderate. This gap is particularly important for teachers who may face unique financial challenges due to changes in their civil status, such as legal separation or widowhood. These life changes can impact income stability and financial responsibilities,

making enhanced financial literacy crucial for effective risk management and long-term financial security.

Therefore, financial literacy training programs should prioritize teachers who are legally separated and widowed, addressing their specific needs in managing finances during transitional periods. By focusing on improving their skills in risk management and other financial areas, such training can empower these teachers to make informed decisions, reduce financial stress, and achieve greater financial stability despite personal challenges. This targeted approach will help ensure that all teachers, regardless of civil status, are equipped with the necessary financial knowledge to thrive.

3. Discussion

This study aimed to determine the civil status profile of the respondents in terms of single, married, widowed, and legally separated. The chapter thereafter included an investigation of the level of teachers' financial savvy in terms of money management; credit and debt management; planning, saving, and investing; and risk management. The subsequent section discussed the significant difference in teacher's financial savvy when grouped according to civil status. The end part determined the respondents that need financial literacy training. The following are the significant findings:

On the civil status profile of teachers, the findings indicated that the majority of teachers were married, followed by those who were single. Fewer teachers were widowed or legally separated. These findings suggest that most teachers tend to be in a stable marital status, which may have implications for their financial responsibilities and priorities. This also points to the possibility that teachers' financial decisions may be influenced by their family struc-

ture and the support systems they have in place.

On the level of teachers' financial savvy, the findings revealed that teachers demonstrated a high level of financial knowledge and behavior in areas such as money management, credit and debt management, as well as planning, saving, and investing. However, when it came to risk management, their financial savvy was found to be at a moderate level. This indicates that while most financial aspects are well understood and practiced by the teachers, risk-related decisions may require further improvement or support. Enhanced training in risk management could help teachers make more informed decisions regarding uncertain financial situations.

On the significant difference in the level of teachers' financial savvy when grouped according to civil status, the results showed a statistically significant variation among the groups. This suggests that a teacher's civil status does influence how they manage and understand financial matters. It reflects the need to consider personal and social factors when designing fi-

nancial education programs. Tailoring financial literacy programs to specific civil status groups could enhance their effectiveness and address the unique needs of each group.

On the civil status profile of teachers that needs training on financial literacy, it is evident that teachers who are widowed or legally separated may require more targeted financial literacy initiatives. While the overall financial savvy of teachers is commendably high, the observed differences based on civil status highlight that specific groups may benefit from additional guidance or support in managing their finances effectively. Providing focused workshops or resources for these groups could improve their financial decision-making and overall financial well-being.

Based on the study's conclusions, it is recommended that the Department of Education

collaborate with financial experts to create targeted financial literacy programs for teachers, especially those who are widowed or legally separated, covering all aspects of financial management including risk. School heads should support teachers' diverse financial needs by offering workshops, resources, and flexible schedules for participation. Teachers are encouraged to actively enhance their financial knowledge and mentor peers to build a financially savvy community. Incorporating financial literacy into the student curriculum is also advised to prepare students for responsible money management. Finally, future research should examine the unique financial challenges faced by teachers of different civil statuses and the long-term effects of financial literacy programs on educators' well-being and performance.

5. References

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